

8T – Isomorphism's and Covariance

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T framework author present the analog of co-variance which is the isomorphism of the manifold from itself to itself. Additional take on the subject of mechanical similarity, which indicate that matter can be created while keeping the manifold stationary. As matter is being created the probability of violation by a prime, i.e. a Boson is increasing, and thus must be taken into consideration.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin N = $2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Let us analyze the idea of co-variance in this framework. The paper will present two roots in which co-variance rise. The idea behind the co-variance is the following sentence – there is only one set of rules. In the context of variational manifolds, there exist only one manifold. The idea of co-variance can firstly be analyze via the notion of isomorphism. In this context, isomorphism would be to state that the manifold is the same manifold; the difference is that observer may watch the manifold in different configurations, i.e. different states, similar to QFT idea in which the phases are independent from the amplitudes, the phases are signaling to a degree of rotation, 8T equivalent would be certain degree of acceleration due to curvature on the manifold. We defined the manifold as the variable "s" so the isomorphism can be put in rigor:

$$\Delta: s \rightarrow s$$

$$s = (M, g)$$

The notion of isomorphism's, of an object which vary but still stay as is, is the mathematical equivalence of physical co-variance, as one believes. In that context, another interesting analog is of the similarity of a mechanical system. In particular is that the equation of motion is left unaltered if multiplied by constant, which applies to cases in which the potential energy is an homogenous function of the co-ordinates. Suppose we would multiply the equations of manifold variation by some factor,

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i * K$$

Assuming manifold invoked stationary:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \tag{1.48}$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i * K = 0$$

The stationarity condition is not altered by scalar multiplication; matter can be created in higher amounts while keeping the manifold stationary. From that argument, we can extract that the potential energy of the manifold is an homogenous function of the metric tensor. That is very different than the QFT formalism which require for each matter created, anti-matter creation keeping the S matrix unvaried. If that was in fact the case, anti-matter would be quite common in the universe which is not the case. That idea of matter anti-matter pairs vanishing to zero, led to the massive difference in estimating the source of dark energy. 8T allows creation of matter while keeping the manifold stationary, matter pairs in such way that no curvature is allowed, that is by the anti-commutation relation of fermions. The result of this construction is that energy is not conserved. That is because matter can morph into energy, and arbitrary variations of the manifold vanish into matter. Those ideas could be somewhat hard to accept, similar to how the discovery of Planck and Heisenberg principle were hard to accept at the time. In certain sense If the QFT idea was right, anti-matter would be as common as matter, as those pair to each other for each matter particle created, which is not the case. The second quantity which is not conserved is the number of violations, as matter being created in larger amounts, there exist higher probability of violations which are prime (or one) amount of curvature to arise from it, to despite the manifold is isomorphic to itself, the number of elements in the subgroup of violations is ever increasing.

$$s = (M, g, \mathcal{F})$$

Let \mathcal{F} be the summation of net variations of all kind, which is a function of time. In the 8T framework:

$$\mathcal{F} = \sum_{i=1}^{i=N_v} p_i^X$$

The subscript is the kind of net variation:

$$\varphi: N_v \rightarrow p_i \tag{2.4}$$

The superscript is the element that absorbed

$$X = e_i; \quad i \in \mathbb{R}$$

Over time, the probability of violations increases as more matter is being created:

$$\mathcal{F}_t < \mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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